

RESEARCH ARTICLE

‘Call the Bluff’ or ‘Build Back Better’—Anti-corruption reforms in post-war Ukraine

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Abstract

The fight against corruption is presented as a leading principle in policy papers and at donor conferences discussing Ukraine's reconstruction. It therefore mirrors the usual narrative surrounding post-war reconstruction and democracy promotion attempts. However, reconstruction aid has historically been used for illicit means by elites and ended up strengthening an uneven system rather than building a resilient and successful country, despite the window of opportunity for the latter. Rather than just proposing principles, this paper therefore poses the question of how actors involved in the reconstruction process can be bound to stick to their previously propagated and formally existing principles. The analysis combines academic and policy-oriented studies and highlights the combined importance of the external and internal dimension for a successful outcome. It proposes a ‘double conditionality’ mechanism, where an independent, technocratic institution holds frozen, Russian assets and partially reimburses Western donors only after successful audits on the reconstruction aid are conducted. This conditionality puts domestic pressure on aid givers to follow through with the anti-corruption conditions formulated beforehand and to call out any reform bluff on Kyiv's side. Paired with a credible EU accession perspective, this can bring about the much-needed stimulus for a build back better scenario.

1 | INTRODUCTION

President Volodymyr Zelensky recently announced that ‘no one will be able to forgive corruption in the future Ukraine, ...[because]... all the corrupt officials [have] fled the nation’ (Bloomberg, 2022). Although this assessment comes too early, it represents one development path because an invasion is usually seen as a good example of an ‘exogenous shock’. Through it, the institutional equilibrium in a country gets significantly shaken up and a potential critical juncture appears ‘that weakens the path-dependent policy trajectory as well as participating actors’ “veto positions” (Collier & Collier, 2002). In the case of post-WWII Europe, ‘the role of external democracy promotion, prior experience with democracy and structural characteristics of the pre-existing autocratic regime’ determined whether a

country experienced a democratic breakthrough following such a shock (Merkel & Gerschewski, 2019: 280).

The interplay between internal and external factors also explains why Ukraine experienced repeated ‘revolutions without regime change’ after 1991, through which under the banner of revolutions, nominally symbolizing critical junctures, the composition of key actors in the system changed but a hybrid system, marked by high levels of corruption, persisted (Matsiyevsky, 2018). Corruption, and the persistence of it, explains in this context how the system functioned and why it was relatively resilient (Pleines, 2019). It therefore represents both a suitable proxy variable for the institutional development and a decisive issue for the outcome of a post-war reconstruction process in institutional but also financial terms.

Practically all references to a potentially successful reconstruction in Ukraine invoke the Marshall Plan, as

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post-conflict countries usually experience an increase of corruption (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014). A comparative study of anti-corruption policy implementation in post-war settings ended up ‘failing to find successful case studies of applied best practices’ (Boucher et al., 2007). This is despite *purported* best efforts of all parties involved: for instance, in its 1999 recommendations for the reconstruction of Kosovo, the Council of Europe underlined that ‘democracy, human rights and the rule of law, [...] *must pervade the entire project*’ (Council of Europe, 1999).

The Lugano Declaration, an outline signed by Ukraine's main supporters, echoes the recommendations for Kosovo by underlining that ‘the rule of law must be systematically strengthened, and corruption *eradicated*’ (Ukraine Recovery Conference, 2022). As this article argues, the case of Ukraine bears the *potential* to see factual outcomes following the initially declared intentions of key actors. Based on an analysis of internal and external factors, joining therefore an increasingly popular strand in the literature that investigates the institutional trajectories of post-conflict states via ‘the consideration of domestic *and* international relations of power’ (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014), it identifies and elaborates two likely development scenarios in Ukraine.

First, the baseline scenario based on past behaviour, in which domestic elites and external actors, that is EU and the G7 states as key signatories of the Lugano Declaration, share a rhetoric of reforms but the former practically undermines them whilst the latter tolerate it by very selectively exercising its leverage. The possible availability of frozen Russian assets to fund reconstruction might satisfy all key stakeholders in this scenario but indicate a missed chance to ‘build back better’.

Second, a building back better case, in which external actors are themselves committed to reform outcomes through a conditional reimbursement mechanism for their support and therefore closely work with Ukrainian civil society organizations (CSOs) to detect reform imitation and use its leverage to intervene and effectively change the incentive structure of Ukrainian elites towards anti-corruption promotion. As public procurement is constituting arguably the main source of corruption in the reconstruction period, the breakthrough scenario can only materialize if a competitive channelling of money in public procurement processes is achieved.

Advocating for the key provisions of the positive scenario can also be seen as ‘calling the bluff’ in reforming Ukraine. This is because a Western agreement to this scenario would indicate a real commitment to reforms on their behalf and the *necessity* to call the bluff in case Ukrainian elites do not share the same enthusiasm in practice. Otherwise, abstaining from pursuing this scenario can also be understood as ‘calling the bluff’ of

Policy Implications

- Russian assets seem in the reconstruction context like an easy fix for Western policy makers to ‘buy off peace’ at home and disburse the bulk share of aid this way. However, this comes along without many incentives for monitoring and execution, which might cement the uneven playing field in the Ukrainian political economy domain.
- Instead, a partial reimbursement mechanism can incentivise Western donors to stick to the principles formulated before a reconstruction process begins. This reimbursement is conditional on the outcomes of independent audits by a Reconstruction Coordination Institution (RCI).
- This RCI should work closely with local CSOs, which have in the past highlighted worrisome developments but not rarely been ignored due to political considerations. By making interaction between the RCI and CSOs institutionalized, the agency of Ukrainian CSOs is significantly strengthened.
- Related to that, a real door towards Europe might have opened that will be an additional motivation for Kyiv's leadership to resist corruption risks – the enormous cost of non-compliance – if this perspective is made credible by Brussels and relies on the RCI input.
- Much will also depend on how Moscow is perceived by the West. The weaker Russia leaves the battlefield at the conclusion of this war, the less it will be able to interfere in Ukraine's post-war reconstruction period. Therefore, this factor also depends on the level of Western military support over the course of the war and should be seen as an additional rationale to increase it.

Western actors, as their ambitious rhetoric does not go along with practical commitments.

This work builds on the author's past studies on high-level anti-corruption reforms in pre-war Ukraine, which were based on semi-structured interviews and document analyses. It stretches the analytical time frame and combines a theoretical base with policy insights and recommendations focusing on high-level corruption. The key value of this contribution is therefore a translation of identified pre-war mechanisms to the current realities and furthering of the formulation of a ‘successful’ post-war reconstruction process. Hence, in contrast to an academic paper in a narrow sense, it

stands at the intersection of theory and practice and holds value for policymakers and scholars alike.

2 | ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

Scholarly literature argues that ‘if the [armed] conflict has destroyed existing patterns of influence, it may paradoxically represent an opportunity to recreate the state on a fair and democratically legitimate basis’ (Rose-Ackerman, 2008). Although the Ukrainian system was nominally democratic before the invasion, the country’s political economic system was in practice dominated by powerful interest groups that influenced much of the policy-making process for their own benefit (Way, 2021). And whilst a conflict carries the opportunity to overcome such a state, it also has the chance to bring about a situation in which ‘power networks are sometimes consolidated in the post-war era, with corruption being used to buy political power and sustain patronage networks, resulting in state capture of public institutions’ (Chene, 2012). Hence, state-capture can be broken as a result of conflict – or increased. Huge financial inflows in the form of foreign aid can enable the latter, as they are ‘a crucial resource for the corrupt state elite’ (Lie, 1997).

Case contextuality is hereby important but has been mostly evaluated in terms of ‘political will’ and ‘capacities’ to combat corruption, seeing the main factor for outcomes almost exclusively in the post-conflict country itself (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014). In accordance with the key factors explaining a democratic breakthrough following WWII, Section 2 therefore first lays out the Ukrainian pre-war system and the nature of Western intervention in it. Connecting then domestic and external aspects on a broader scale, it looks at the reasons for the lack of global, anti-corruption breakthrough cases of Western reconstruction efforts in the past decades and shows how Ukraine differs to these cases. The analytical section assesses the war’s effect on the Ukrainian system and lays out the two scenarios based on the previous elaborations and the conditions for a successful post-war reconstruction period. This approach follows the points set out in the conceptual Figure 1 in below:

FIGURE 1 Analytical framework. Own presentation.

2.1 | The Ukrainian pre-war system

2.1.1 | Initial situation (point 1)

The pre-war political economy system in Ukraine was dominated by oligarchic groups, sometimes called clans, with individuals combining political and economic power at their top (Minakov, 2019). Due to regional east–west divisions, a balance was created between nominally pro-Western and pro-Russian oligarchs (Way, 2021). Whilst theoretically competing against each other, these groups joined forces when a threat to this system emerged, such as the fight against corruption (Pleines, 2019). Through this, ‘veto positions’ existed that locked Ukraine in a state of hybridity. Most economic success in this system stemmed not from companies’ competitiveness, but from privileged access to state resources (Pikulik, 2019). Corruption was the main mechanism for generating economic gains, whilst it ensured loyalty and distributed spoils within groups (Pleines, 2019).

The influence of Ukraine’s external partners on this system was characterized by a persistent gap between narrative and reality: in the case of the EU, ‘despite [its] pervasive political and legal rhetoric of democracy and human rights promotion, actual policy seems to match rhetoric only when consistency is “cheap”; otherwise, it is driven by a host of other geopolitical, economic or security interests’ (Schimmelfennig, 2015: 16). This finding is echoed in the context of other Western actors, showcasing an ‘inconsistent application [of conditionality] with lack of any *credible* threat on the part of donors’ (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019: 255). Being aware of this, Ukrainian elites, despite their constant rhetoric of democracy and serious commitments to anti-corruption reforms, could engage in reform imitation and/or omission, undermining the practical functionality of anti-corruption legislation. The establishment of multiple anti-corruption institutions was part of the conditional support of Western actors in Ukraine and described as a main reform success.

However, these institutions immediately found themselves under attack by oligarchic groups: e.g., proceedings were transferred from anti-corruption institutions to the ordinary judiciary system or security services

(Transparency International, 2022). This is because the judiciary had remained mostly unreformed and not the rule of law decided over outcomes but preferential access to judges. Although several reform attempts were launched, under the cover of reforms the increase of executive grip over judicial institutions was observed, for instance when President Zelensky single-handedly replaced a set of judges in the Constitutional Court in a move criticized by the Venice Commission (Melkozerova, 2022). To circumvent unreformed courts, a special High Anti-corruption Court was established. However, representing the end of the anti-corruption chain, it could not work effectively without proper functioning of the lower institutions. Yet, upon facing corruption accusations, even members of the president's own entourage, such as the controversial Deputy of the Presidential Office, Oleg Tatarov, openly attacked the investigative institution NABU and called for the resignation of its head. This, and the transfer and later closure of his case by ordinary courts effectively 'discredited the work of the entire anti-corruption system [...and...] questioned the independence of anti-corruption bodies'. (Transparency International, 2022).

The omission and selective application of good governance institutions set up under conditionality pressure also included reforms that were at one point deemed 'sustainable' by scholars, such as the innovative procurement platform ProZorro (Nizhnikau, 2022: 202). In the 'Great Construction', Zelensky's effort to boost road construction which used half of Ukraine's own COVID fund, the open participation in ProZorro tenders was significantly limited, through which 'the companies that remained were the same ones that received lucrative offers in the past' (Sorokin, 2021). Through kickbacks, prices were inflated, and Ukraine lost in two years a sum equal to *at least* 1% of its GDP and audits of those roads showed that sometimes less than required asphalt was used, further increasing the illicit rent (Sorokin, 2021). Ukraine's most expensive road project before the war, the 'Kyiv Ring Road', was directly called 'highway robbery' as it entirely omitted ProZorro following an amendment in the legislative process (Sorokin, 2021). Although strongly criticized by local CSOs, Western advisors abstained from voicing any official criticism, highlighting the generally established limited influence of CSOs to affect these processes on their own (Richter, 2023).

Three reasons explain the lack of Western intervention in this case, which serves as a blueprint for the broader selectivity of intervention in the Ukrainian case. First, the money at stake was mostly Ukrainian, having been diverted from different ministries for the COVID fund, through which practical tools and incentives to address this issue by conditionality were missing (Sorokin, 2021). Secondly, voicing criticism in this situation will have been overshadowed by 'geopolitical considerations', particularly vis-à-vis Russia. Moscow

was traditionally invested in influencing Ukrainian politics, promoting pro-Russian politicians, and offering help not for the anti-corruption reforms demanded by the West, but for geopolitical concessions (Way, 2015). Whilst this influence decreased after the Euromaidan, pro-Russian oligarchs and parliamentarians could still misuse Western criticism of shortcomings to discredit reforms and to play into the Russian narrative of a failed state. Hence, in the absence of credible benefits to give to Ukrainian ruling elites, other than limited financial support, severe criticism might have even backfired and strengthened these pro-Russian forces who were even more hostile to reforms (Richter, 2023). Thirdly, it was Western companies that partially benefited from these constellations, such as the American building company Bechtel or the Turkish Onur, decreasing the incentive to criticize even further (Sorokin, 2021).

Geopolitical and sovereignty constraints and in part own commercial interests of Western actors, combined with a questionable reform drive of elites and limited intervention capabilities of the civil society brought about the outcome of 'revolution[s] without regime change'. Conditionality was therefore particularly strong when the need for this support was huge and when it was about the formal enactment of legislations. This was mostly in the first post-Euromaidan years the case. Later, the need for support decreased and with it shortcomings as well omissions became commonplace. The selectivity of intervention is not unique to Ukraine but a general finding across different Western actors and recipients, with different factors weighted in (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019). Even in cases where no direct conditionality is present, this is a missed chance, as exemplary for the EU, the 'highest impact of EU intervention is in raising the corruption problem on the public agenda' (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019). Hence, the external selectivity of intervention, even if only vocally, further reduces the potential of the domestic channel of change.

This bears particular relevance in the EU context. Although it is sometimes argued that a membership perspective is the lacking factor for reforms in some countries, a deterioration of democratic standards can be observed in countries with such a formal perspective and even within the EU itself (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019). A candidacy status can serve only as a reform anchor, requiring *some* political will to reform, or at least to join the EU through reforms, and a *credible* membership perspective to have this anchor working. The later has become an issue due to 'accession fatigue' in the EU, which 'is both a reflex response to a rather inchoate set of EU problems and simultaneously helps to structure a *culture of partial or non-compliance with EU laws*' (O'Brennan, 2014: 239). It effectively turns into a self-fulfilling prophecy and vicious circle as the lack of reforms in candidate countries, caused *in part* by the lack of a *credible* accession perspective, is used to deny this credible accession perspective, creating a

negative feedback loop. Selective intervention contributes in this context to that as it fails to fully call out non-compliance, perhaps knowing of the limited, de-facto EU perspective anyway.

2.2 | Assessing Western post-war reconstruction anti-corruption failure in the past

Traditional studies on reconstruction outcomes are characterized by a 'dichotomy between state capacity and lack of [political] will [of the leadership]' (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014). As institutions determining anti-corruption outcomes in Ukraine show, state capacity is not a problem, but the (lack of) political will to not build in exceptions and omissions. Kyiv's Western partners were also missing political will to intervene in these cases, despite Ukrainian CSOs calling for it. The role of Western actors in reconstruction processes mirrors this, as '[they] are eager to prescribe policies to deal with corruption, [but] at the same time they often signal a tolerance of it' (Lindberg & Orjuela, 2014). For example, in Kosovo, the EU had executive powers (that is, capacity) in the form of the EULEX mission to *directly* fight against high-level corruption, but the EU largely abstained from using its powers (Proksik, 2018), which highlights once again the impact of other factors explaining the gap between rhetoric, capabilities, and actual policy in external anti-corruption promotion.

Post-conflict settings are particularly susceptible to instability, and corruption can be perceived as a lesser evil compared to renewed conflicts, a concept known as 'buying off peace' (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014). Intervenors are thus incentivized to prioritize stability over reform. However, this approach is a short-term fix because 'if the problem is not addressed it can undermine other efforts to create a stable, well-functioning state with popular legitimacy' (Rose-Ackerman, 2008). As seen in Afghanistan 'security and political goals consistently trumped strong anticorruption actions', but in the end 'corruption undermined the U.S. mission' (SIGAR, 2016). This pattern is also detectable in the Balkans, as in Kosovo and Bosnia anti-corruption reform attempts were overshadowed by stability considerations caused by ethnic cleavages and existing state capture, leading to poor reconstruction results (Belloni & Strazzari, 2014; Proksik, 2018). The inherent instability of these polities led to the rise 'new transnational crime groups [whose] profits are made by destabilizing the state and its structures' (Shelley, 2005), creating even further reform resistance. This symbolizes the emergence of a negative feedback loop once an initial, unfavourable path of action is taken.

However, in contrast to the example countries mentioned before, Ukraine is characterized, despite all its problems, by a relatively resilient state with a very

consolidated society, especially since the invasion. Corrupt crime groups might still emerge, or prevail, but those of a more traditional type, which 'have [historically] profited from valuable public construction contracts', through which 'economic development of the state is therefore of paramount importance' (Shelley, 2005). As corruption and *relative* development come together in this case, the huge reconstruction infusions might overshadow the negative effects of corruption for the broad part of Ukrainian society. Exemplified through mechanisms like that of the 'Great Construction' projects, this increases the importance of CSOs in spotting and Western actors in preventing it, *if long-term development of Ukraine is truly prioritized by the latter as officially stated*.

The financial context of Ukraine's reconstruction is favourable for this because the required funds, being a multiple of its annual GDP, set it apart from many EU and non-EU countries where the impact of conditionality was very limited to begin with as the sum linked to this mechanism was relatively small (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019). At the same time, the sum needed for the reconstruction of Kosovo was in *relative* terms also enormous (see Gligorov, 2007), but a much higher *total* sum is needed for the reconstruction of Ukraine due to a roughly 20 times bigger population. As the literature postulates, 'the combination of salience and substantive public opinion always has an effect and is of substantial policy importance' (Burstein, 2003). This will severely increase objective salience of this issue in the Western public and preferences stemming from societal pressure will play a much bigger role. Kosovo's size made 'buying off peace' more tolerable, whereas uncovering large-scale instances of corruption in Ukraine could threaten societal approval in aid-providing countries.

Scholarly literature points therefore to the importance of the source of funds. The reconstruction of Iraq is a compelling case as dubious Iraqi funds were repatriated in cash by the US, which were not subject to much scrutiny and ended up fuelling the circle of corruption (Le Billon, 2008). This echoes the 'Great Construction' and the Western treatment of Ukrainian funds. Meanwhile, Western money directly spent in Iraq, was under significant oversight and transparency provisions were installed. Repeated calls by Western politicians and experts to directly use Russian assets for the reconstruction of Ukraine are in this context morally right and politically less sensitive as they can be seen as buying off (political) peace at home.

However, they take away the incentive away from Western societies to be particularly concerned about reconstruction outcomes and therefore also from Western governments to intervene. Combined with the weakness of Ukrainian CSOs and the traditional drive of domestic elites to hollow out reforms, a return to the modus operandi of the pre-war period might emerge. As such, omissions and exemptions to good governance

institutions and the quiet tolerance of it by Western actors would remain prevalent, fuelling corruption and cementing an uneven playing field. Given Ukraine's remarkable degree of relative stability, through which the traditional 'buying off peace' mechanism might not apply to Ukraine, it would indicate a deliberately missed window of opportunity to build back better.

3 | ANALYSIS

To proceed with its argument and following the logic of [Figure 1](#), this part first assesses the changes through the war and then proposes how the reconstruction process must be designed to build back better. The ultimate objective: devising a way for Ukraine to win not just the war against Russia, but also use this critical juncture to defeat corruption and move towards full democracy.

3.1 | Changes since the Full-Scale invasion

Assessing Ukraine's current democratic state since the war broke out, an ambiguous picture is retrieved. It displays the influence of leverage and the simultaneous desire of current Ukrainian elites to increase their relative power. This takes place in the context of a significant weakening of oligarchic groups as many principal actors left Ukraine prior to or during the war. This includes people like Viktor Medvedchuk, one of the leaders of the 'Donetsk clan' and close Putin ally (Skorkin, 2023). The clan's political arm, the 'Opposition Platform – For Life', a notorious anti-reform block in the Rada, was forbidden and dissolved. Those parliamentarians from the group that did not flee abroad founded new, smaller, and nominally pro-European entities. Visible through this, a pro-Russian vector, even under the slogan of 'neutrality', is effectively dead in Ukraine, which will also *conceptually* decrease the Russian influence over and geopolitical considerations of the West in Ukraine (Skorkin, 2023).

Secondly, even the oligarchs who have not fled or been expelled from the country have seen their fortunes diminishing. These include actors like Rinat Akhmetov, Viktor Pinchuk, or Konstantyn Zhevago whose assets were damaged to various degrees due to the war (Liamets, 2023). According to Forbes, the richest Ukrainians lost around *half of their wealth*, or \$20 bn, by the end of 2022 (Semenova, 2022). In addition, others lost their citizenship, such as Ihor Kolomoyskiy, or sold their media empires, such as Akhmetov (Liamets, 2023). Their influence was a key reason for the situation before the war as they acted in their own self-interest to preserve the system built on corruption in which they enjoyed a huge competitive advantage.

However, parallel to the weakening of their relative position, their veto power to preserve the status quo also decreased significantly.

As a result, two broader development paths become visible: a positive one, in which the diffusion and relative weakening of many anti-reform actors might finally lead to a tipping point in which corruption as the *modus operandi* can finally be overcome. However, there is also the possibility of a less optimistic scenario, one in which only the relative balance of different anti-reform actors has shifted, leading to the emergence of a more centralized version of corruption which grants competitive advantage to a smaller circle of people with access to a single centre of power.

A noteworthy change concerning the *formal* context of EU-Ukraine relations with the granting of the accession perspective in June 2022 has emerged that *could* pave the way for the positive scenario. Evidenced by several recommendations that Brussels issued, most of which focused on rule of law matters, to be implemented before the commencement of membership negotiations can happen, they unblocked almost overnight key anti-corruption reforms that were frozen for a considerable time (Stefanishyna, 2023). An example is the instalment of the elected head of Ukraine's Special Anticorruption Prosecutor Office (SAPO), one of the new key institutions set up since 2014 (Melkozerova, 2022). Having been repeatedly blocked in the past, this about-face is evidence for the factual strength that conditionality has when the execution of certain reforms is directly coupled to credible (political) benefits but also demonstrates the lack of an endogenous reform will of Ukrainian elites.

A similar case in point is the notorious Kyiv Administrative District Court, which was long an important instrument in the hands of anti-reform groups. Through this court, which also held jurisdiction over government-related people and issues, many anti-corruption proceedings were effectively terminated. Despite being so controversial, only in December 2022 (allegedly after its chairman, Pavlo Volk, was put on a US sanctions list for bribery) the parliament terminated the court's mandate (Melkozerova, 2022), another potential example of the current strength of Western conditionality.

However, this was accompanied by several controversial developments that weaken this positive picture. First, President Zelensky signed Law no. 2736-IX, which officially seeks an approximation of Ukraine's Financial Action Task Force standards to those of the EU and was hailed by official representatives as an important reform. Yet, a controversial amendment was built into it in the parliamentary process, which removes the obligation on former state officials, including former presidents, to declare their assets beyond 3 years after leaving public office (Focus Ukraine, 2022). The asset declaration system is a crucial instrument and

foundational aspect of the anti-corruption institutional chain. Previously, many groups sought exemptions from it. This mirrors the exemptions built into other instruments, such as ProZorro, and past approaches in which elites have repeatedly tried to increase their grip over institutions, or decrease the grip of institutions over them, under the banner of reforming or repairing them (Richter, 2023).

Second, there are worrisome tendencies with respect to the Constitutional Court itself. Despite the undisputed need for its reform, a law was signed by the president that amends the appointment procedure in a way that allows blocking independent candidates (Melkozerova, 2022). Although it foresees a decisive role for independent (foreign) experts in an advisory group, its votes can be blocked by government officials in it and candidates not receiving the approval of the advisory group can still be appointed by the president. In effect, it institutionalizes the president's power over the CCU, but is being sold in Western outlets by official Ukrainian representatives as a breakthrough reform (Stefanishyna, 2023).

Third, that such processes can lead to questionable results is visible in current NABU proceedings. Despite the involvement of Western experts in the selection procedure, the president chose Semen Kryvonos as its new head, whose candidacy was rejected by two of the six selection committee members. This sparked controversy as he did not have prior anti-corruption experience, had faced corruption charges in the past, and is supposedly close to the key actors in the presidential office (Antac, 2023). Tellingly, looking at the track of record of NABU since then, criticism was voiced by Ukrainian CSOs that can be summarized as the fear 'that a clampdown on corruption is being used to frame high profile business advocates of state reform, raising wider doubts about Ukraine's internal political trajectory' (Wintour, 2023).

In its entirety, these attempts by the president and his entourage, especially considering the context in which they have occurred, can potentially be seen as attempts to fill the vacuum left by the relative power loss of most oligarchic groups for their own sake. They can also be seen as the continuation of the traditional game that actors in this system play in which they push back against reforms, seeing how far they can extend their power before Western actors intervene and demand their resolution in exchange for the continuation of support. An abstention of criticism is in this case attributed to the war, the associated geopolitical situation, and in order to not give ground to Russian propaganda (Melkozerova, 2022). The latter two therefore mirror past reasons for selective interventions. However, when reform imitation for the sake of the centralization of power (CCU case), reform exemptions (case of asset declarations), and questionable appointments and persecutions (NABU case) at such important nodes at

such a crucial point in time become the norm again, then corruption risks cannot be averted during the reconstruction process and a critical juncture is missed. Illicit flows might simply change their channels and the pool of key beneficiaries might decrease.

3.2 | Designing the reconstruction to mitigate corruption risks

The previous elaboration reveals a mixed picture in which conditionality of Western actors that bring some progress are accompanied by subtle reform capture. As the agency for reconstruction and reforms always has been and will explicitly remain on the Ukrainian side, the role of its Western partners is to provide appropriate incentive structures to operationalize key good governance institutions which can withstand the appeal of power consolidation or at least to openly call the bluff of reform imitation, increasing public pressure. Due to elevated corruption risks in the post-war period, a power vacuum left by the relative weakening of oligarchs, the past weaknesses of Ukrainian CSOs and the difficulty to predict their characteristics in the future, and a justified 'war hero' status of the Ukrainian leadership, this external channel is arguably the most promising one to induce a change.

However, in a realistic baseline scenario, one that does not build back *better*, past behaviour persists. It is characterized by elevated prices due to corruption and a centralization of political and economic power due to the decrease of an oligarchic counterweight. In it, the reform commitment of the Ukrainian leadership is mainly in word but not in deed. This stems from the benefits that it gains from the system but also due to the lack of a credible EU membership perspective that could serve as a reform anchor. This lack is a result of the enlargement fatigue and the lack of reforms in Ukraine, interlinking both aspects. Russian assets represent an easy fix that satisfies all key actors in the short term, but disincentivise any serious reform drive as the benefits for reform compliance, which are limited in any case in this scenario, do not match with the costs for elites that have a power vacuum they can fill now. The country, nevertheless, sees reconstruction and relative development, but the system remains undemocratic and fails to live up to its potential. Hence, it builds back, but not better. The 'Great Construction' serves as a blueprint for this scenario and the semi-complicit role of Western actors in it.

In contrast, a build back better scenario is based on an a-priori commitment to comprehensive anti-corruption reforms by Western actors throughout the entire post-war period, decreasing this way the weight of other considerations along the way. So that the vacuum left by anti-reformist forces is more likely to be replaced by a rule of law and not a president state, or at

for investigating and punishing fraud likewise increases the cost for corrupt behaviour, decreasing the incentive for engaging in procurement fraud in the first place. Hence, focusing on a solid procurement system would automatically come along with beneficial, broader institutional effects for the long run. Especially in the Ukrainian case, where the existing procurement system has already been described as cutting edge, access and exemptions are the issues. The Kyiv Ring Road is just one example. After the war there will be hundreds of such roads, and exceptions to transparent procurement should only be allowed in absolutely sensitive cases, such as when military procurement is at stake. Another issue is the access to auctions. In the case of the 'Great Construction', the entry requirements were tailor-made for specific, designated companies, allowing the emergence of a 'road cartel' (Sorokin, 2021). The requirements for participation at ProZorro auctions should be the minimum needed to ensure the maximal degree of competitiveness. This also concerns all technicalities, for example digital signatures.

The same applies to the anti-corruption infrastructure. The traditional approach of either omitting these institutions when they started investigating the country's leadership, entirely blocking them, or appointing people with questionable links to the leadership must be terminated. Selection procedures must be reviewed and, if necessary, amended. The same applies to ordinary courts. The goal must be the independence of these institutions from executive influence. This is of particular relevance for the impact that civil society organizations can have. Past investigations of supposed corruption cases that only commenced after revelations of investigative journalists happened show that independent and integral anti-corruption institutions give civil society actors indirectly increased ownership over, agency in, and influence on this process.

Based on those targets, in the first step, Western actors would disburse money directly from their budgets to cover the first round of reconstruction needs, creating Western, domestic pressure for their proper use through what can be called 'soft conditionality' (that is, disbursement conditional on the formal implementation of required reform steps). This would concern the procurement system and the investigation of fraud infrastructure in such a way that (a) exceptions are formally avoided for channelling the money and (b) all institutions are fully operational, as outlined above.

In a close exchange with Ukrainian CSOs, as indicated by all light blue arrows with the number 2, the RCI would thoroughly audit the outcome of financial flows from the first funding round. Just as there are clear thresholds to meet in corporate auditing, so too would *predetermined* benchmarks be used to assess the success of the 'soft conditionality' approach and its translation into practice, decreasing the weight of 'other issues'. The EU and other donors would conduct

their own assessments and the RCI, in conjunction with Ukrainian CSOs, would provide these donors with their assessment.

This is particularly important for the third step, namely the partial reimbursement of Western donors based on the achievement of the aforementioned benchmarks. Only in case the 'soft conditionality' approach materializes in successful financial reconstruction efforts, hence reducing corruption, are Russian assets used to partially refund Western contributions to Kyiv, as indicated by arrow number 3.1. Then, Western donors would once again provide Kyiv with reconstruction money in Step 3.2, however this time based on the feedback received from the auditing report from Step 2. In case major flaws in the practical dimensions of procurement and/or investigation of fraud were found, any further money will be made conditional upon creating additional safeguard measures, as identified by the auditing reports, and especially any RCI recommendations.

The financial disbursement is accompanied by a political process of EU integration. For this, the outcomes of the audits of round number two, the factual implementation of a successful post-war reconstruction infrastructure, will be foundational. The conditionality on this integration process creates additional incentives to comply, or additional costs of non-compliance. By having a noteworthy financial stake in this process, Western actors will be bound to call out a potential reform bluff due to domestic pressure. Simultaneously, considering overwhelming support for EU membership within Ukrainian society, threatening this broader goal for individual economic interests of politically associated elites might be very risky for any government in Kyiv. This is, however, conditional upon providing a credible EU perspective by Brussels, which means overcoming expansion fatigue. Being in part a self-fulfilling prophecy, having a crucial, financial interest in a successful reform process, Western countries would automatically be pushing for such an outcome. Such an outcome, in turn, could effectively overcome accession fatigue as a reformed Ukraine could be considered an asset to the Union and accession easier sold to domestic audiences in EU members states. As the reconstruction process is envisioned to proceed for at least 10 years, Steps 2 and 3 would become repeating processes over this timeframe.

4 | CONCLUSION

The historical record of Western post-war reconstruction efforts shows that too often have they provided ripe ground for corruption among elites in war-torn countries, sometimes directly and sometimes indirectly by simply tolerating this phenomenon. This mirrors the partial tolerance of corruption in Ukraine in the post-2014 period,

where formal provisions were often resolutely forced only to turn a blind eye to the practical problems raised by Ukrainian CSOs.

However, on the institutional ruins left by Russia's invasion, a possible critical juncture has emerged with two different directions. As the literature stipulates, in such 'situations of uncertainty ...[the]... decisions of important actors are causally decisive for the selection of one path of institutional development over other possible paths' (Capoccia, 2015). Just as with the fight on the military battlefield against Russia, Western assistance seems decisive to tip the scale on the battlefield against corruption in Ukraine, regardless of the intentions of the post-war Ukrainian leadership. Yet, Russian assets seem in this context like an easy fix for Western policy makers to 'buy off peace' at home and disburse the bulk share of aid without many incentives for sticking to the ambitious principles elaborated before reconstruction begins. Considering past and current realities, the likely outcome will be a persisting, uneven playing field in Ukraine, in which power centralization and corruption get covered by *relative* development, of which the 'Great Construction' is a telling example, but Ukraine misses the opportunity to build back better.

Considering the potential, long-term gains, Western actors should learn from past reconstruction/intervention shortcomings and *bind* themselves to be as ambitious and strict as necessary *now*. Particularly as circumstances in Ukraine, not least its consolidated society, are highly favourable to not treat fighting corruption like a second-best option. Deciding to make partial reimbursement conditional on the outcomes of independent audits by an RCI, which closely works with local CSOs, goes along with noticeable agency transfer to the international level. However, 'international institutions can have binding properties that solve credible commitment problems' (Eilstrup-Sangiovanni & Verdier, 2005). This approach can therefore be the much-needed solution to the commitment problem on the Western side to overcome selective interventions and possibly even the self-fulfilling expansion fatigue. Through this, a real door towards Europe can be opened and the enormous cost of non-compliance, that is not fulfilling Ukrainian society's dream of Europe, will be a major incentive for Kyiv's leadership to resist corruption risks—if this perspective is made credible by Brussels through committing itself to reform success and when it relies on the RCI input, hence bringing in a technical layer that actively takes up concerns of Ukrainian CSOs.

Effective constraints for all actors are therefore conceptually possible and will result in building back better. The West has time and again 'bought off peace' in the short-term, only to be later confronted with its past shortcomings. Facing therefore two options of

how to handle Russian assets and design reconstruction efforts, opting for the easier one and knowing its likely outcome, can be equated with calling the bluff of Western actors' commitment to a successful outcome despite its rhetoric. Of course, a beneficial scenario might still materialize in the baseline scenario, but this would require an endogenous change of the attitude of the Ukrainian leadership or overcoming Ukrainian CSOs weaknesses, for which there is currently *no empirical evidence*.

Other than relying on hope, Western actors should therefore take the ambitious path and become a-priori *and financially* committed to the outcome themselves. Through this, they will be forced to call out a potential reform bluff on Kyiv's side, increasing societal and political pressure on its leadership, particularly as this perspective comes along with a credible EU perspective due to the West's own stake in the process. Through this, the costs of non-compliance are further elevated and the materialization of the breakthrough scenario more likely.

Yet, 'national interests' might constitute major obstacles, especially where handling such huge sums by an RCI is concerned, and Russian assets seem to be a solution that satisfies political elites in the short run. Looking into the future, however, the core question is what benefits the Ukrainian society, and how can Ukraine become an integral member of and true asset to the European family, which can potentially even break the chain of expansion fatigue. Looking at the poor results of recent Western democracy promotion, a new, ambitious approach is needed. The question therefore is whether the West is finally willing under these relatively favourable circumstances to create a 'double conditionality', or whether it keeps exercising selective interventions, bringing very likely the same outcomes, and missing this window of opportunity. It is therefore time to start an attempt at seriously building back better or to call the bluff of being serious about it.

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